

How to quickly write an essay

A little survival guide to quickly give your boss a detailed, well-written report. I will share with you tips and tricks on how to write an essay quickly and efficiently. Before you start reading, I recommend that you familiarize yourself with the [assignment writing help](#) service. Always carefully select the services that will help you complete your assignments.

If your boss asks you for a report, he needs more information to guide him in his decision-making. He might, for example, want to know the general level of satisfaction with certain suppliers or wish to have concrete proposals to improve the efficiency of his service. Here is a four-step manual unearthed for you on [blog-assistantes.fr](#):

Validate

Always take care to specify the request. Your boss's expectations must be clear and above all leave no room for improvisation: What is the context? What are the reasons for the report? What does he expect from you? Does he already have information or are there already documents on the subject?

Collecting and processing [information](#)

Gather all the information you have: internal and external information, notes, reports. Then select only the essentials.

Development of the plan

1. Introduction

The report must include an introduction that indicates the purpose of the report, its relevance, and its importance. Be brief, to the point, and above all, complete in case you need to proofread it several months later.

2. Development

Development is the heart of the analysis and consists of three distinct segments: the statement of the observation and the facts surrounding the situation, the analysis of the facts, the positive points and the negative points, and, finally, the recommendations to resolve the situation setting out their advantages, disadvantages and the means to implement them. The argument must be solid.

3. The conclusion

The third part of the plan: the conclusion. It must be an answer to the question asked. You must go back to your recommendations and focus on the solution found.

The final draft

The shape is important for easy reading, don't forget. Your sentences should be short, the vocabulary precise and the paragraphs well structured. The headings should refer to the different parts. Do you have additional information? To simplify the text, append them at the end of the document. Also, think about tables and graphs that can help to understand. Finally, if your report is longer than three pages, be sure to include a summary.

I hope my article helped you write a quality essay quickly. Either way, remember this skill takes a lot of practice. Good luck!

Related resources:

[How to stay focused: 8 tips](#)

[3 mistakes all students make](#)